

The Influence of Self-Concept on the Tendency of Body Dysmorphic Disorder of Beauty Salon and Fitness Centre Customers in Malang

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Abstract : The aim of the research is to understand the influence of self concept on the tendency for body dysmorphic disorder among beauty salon and fitness centre customers in Malang. Subjects in this study amounted to 200 of beauty salon and fitness centre customers in Malang. Subjects completed a self-concept scale and the tendency of body dysmorphic scale. This study was analyzed using simple linear regression. The result shows that there are 14% influence of self concept on the tendency of body dysmorphic disorder among customers of beauty salon and fitness centre in Malang.

Keywords : self concept, tendency of body dysmorphic disorder, beauty salon and fitness centre customers, Malang

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